
Research

Innovative Geotechnical Solutions: Comparative Study of Helical Pile Foundation System for Bridge Construction in Pakistan

Muhammad Tahir^{1*}, Partab Rai², Huang Yao³

^{1,2,3}Department of Civil Engineering and Department of Geotechnical Engineering,
Southwest Jiaotong University, Sichuan, China

Abstract: This research explores the feasibility and efficiency of helical pile foundation systems for bridge construction, specifically focusing on the challenges faced in the region of River Indus in Ghazi Ghat, Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan. The primary objective is to assess the viability of helical piles as a more sustainable, cost-effective, and technically efficient alternative to conventional pile foundations, particularly in challenging geotechnical conditions.

The study begins with a comprehensive review of existing foundation methods, highlighting the limitations of traditional pile systems in terms of environmental impact, cost, and adaptability to diverse soil profiles. The helical pile foundation, with its unique screw-like design, offers potential benefits including reduced installation time, immediate load-bearing capacity, and minimal environmental footprint. The research methodology incorporates a comparative analysis using advanced finite element method (FEM) simulations. These simulations, conducted via Plaxis-2D, evaluate the performance of helical piles against conventional piles under varying soil conditions and load scenarios.

Key aspects of the study include assessing the load-bearing capacity of helical piles, installation efficiency, and environmental implications. The research also explores the adaptation of international design codes for helical piles in the local context, considering regional soil characteristics and engineering practices. The results demonstrate a significant improvement in load capacity, reduction in the number of piles required, and overall cost savings when using helical piles. Moreover, the environmental benefits of this method are underscored, highlighting its alignment with sustainable engineering practices.

In conclusion, the study advocates for the integration of helical pile systems in bridge construction projects in Pakistan, particularly in regions with similar geotechnical challenges as those found at the River Indus site. The research underscores the need for continued innovation in foundation engineering, advocating for a shift towards more sustainable and efficient practices. Further studies are recommended to explore the long-term performance and broader applications of helical pile systems in various construction contexts.

Keywords: Helical Piles, Geotechnical Engineering, Bridge Construction, Finite Element Analysis, Sustainable Infrastructure

*Corresponding Author

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Introduction

Cast in place bored Piling is widely employed as one of the most common deep foundation systems worldwide. There are two types of casts in place piles. One is called friction pile and the other is end bearing pile. Friction piles are used in case of cohesive soils whereas the end bearing piles are planned in cohesion-less soil profiles. In most cases, piles are designed as friction-cum-bearing piles because most soil types are spread between cohesive and cohesion-less soils. There are certain major issues related with this construction practice. First of all, it needs a lot of arrangements at site, such as drilling rig, crane, excavator, tremie pipe, skilled labor, storage and mass of water and arrangement of concrete delivery from batching plant to the site. In case anyone of the above-mentioned resources is missing, the piling activity cannot be performed. The other major problem with the drilled piles is non-sustainability of the boreholes overnight in case of wet boring and no working time frame as there can be any obscure hindrance underground. In case of collapse of borehole there are a lot of nuisances at site.

Pile foundations normally support high rise buildings, electric transmission towers and water tanks etc. All of these structures are subjected to axial compression, uplift and overturning moments due to wind, seismic and other lateral loading. In developed countries, helical piles are considered better choice for resistance of the above-mentioned actions. The main benefit of using helical piles is ease of installation, control of noise over job site and reusability are studied by Sinha et al. (2021). Other advantages include diminished spoil generation during installation and ability to take load immediately also investigate by Dhattrak et al. (2022). Moreover, this helps in cost reduction as compared to the conventional bored piles. The load carrying capacity of helical pile can be increased by increasing diameter of pile, helical blade diameter or number of helices per pile length. Helical Piles are environmentally friendly, and its performance depends on soil strata, soil-pile interaction and pile geometry is discussed by the Sprince and Pakrastinsh (2010). The capacity of a helical pile can be associated with the driving torque Harnish (2015). Furthermore, the helical pile exhibits more uplift capacity than the bored cast-in-situ RCC pile researched by Joseph et al (2022). Moreover, under dry conditions, helical piles offer more resistance against ground motion as compared to RCC piles, whereas in moist condition this capacity is reduced Hussein and Naggar (2022).

In this research, the focus will be on the analysis of helical pile foundation system using finite elements software. Plaxis-2d is a famous tool in analyzing the automotive, aerospace, and industrial product industries. The software is popular with academic and research institutions due to the extensive material modeling capability, and the program's capacity to be tailored. Numerical modeling will be done by means of software in order to be able to model the helical pile diameter, depth, helical blade diameter and number of helices per pile length George et al. (2020) and Karkush et al. (2021). Other parameters of interest are installation torque, effects of installation, installation speed, uplift capacity and model pile results proposed by Spagnoli et al. (2020). Research has shown that the group interaction of helical piles is reduced as compared to conventional piles Lanyi-Bennett and Deng (2019). A review of numerical, analytical and

experimental studies carried out on conventional and advanced piles subjected to monotonic and cyclic lateral loading has been presented by Rathod et al. (2019). Recycling torque considering single plate helix was investigated Ding et al. (2019). Therefore, this research is based on a location where river Indus divides the Punjab province of Pakistan into eastern and western part. A bridge is required to be built parallel to the existing bridge. We will design foundation for this bridge using a numerical model based on the design philosophy of helical pile and compare the results with the design and cost of cast in place piles.

The overall goal of the research program is to find a sustainable alternative to the hard-earned site activities. Piling is considered one of the most tedious jobs not only due to difficulties during execution but also time taken by its strengthening and testing before critical activities such as casting of transoms can start. This normally leads to cost and time over runs dragging projects behind schedule. The specific aim of this thesis is to deduce an economical and easy solution to the piling of foundations. Another unique advantage that helical pile has over bored or cast piles is its reusability in case of temporary construction. It can easily be dismantled and installed on the new location.

This research has its vitality in the field of geotechnical engineering as well as construction management. The difficulties encountered during the construction of cast in situ RCC piles are enormous. Experience has shown that the piling activity is a very crucial activity. There are a lot of draw backs of the procedures being adopted currently in Pakistan. The most common problem in waterlogged areas is the collapse of pile bore holes. At times it happens when the pile drilling is just about to finish. These results in significant delays in the project timeline as well as loss of machinery fuel and drilling effort. The other issue is unanticipated extra quantity of concrete. Normally the construction managers order concrete in extra quantities in order to cope with any unexpected situation at site. The left-over concrete must be disposed of in some areas. This process increases the construction waste which is hazardous to the atmosphere. There is a need to find a sustainable solution to the above-mentioned process that produces robust results with lesser mechanical effort.

The overall goal of the research program is to find a sustainable alternative to the hard-earned site activities. Piling is considered one of the most tedious jobs not only due to difficulties during execution but also time taken by strengthening and testing of piles before critical activities such as casting of transoms can start. There is a lot of annoyance during execution of concrete cast in situ piles. During this thesis, viable solutions will be proposed considering the Pakistani atmosphere and hindrances in construction by considering helical pile an alternative solution. For this purpose, we want to achieve a solution for deep foundation which is much easier and cost effective. Furthermore, in the areas of building where piling is required for temporary purposes, helical piles have a major advantage over bored RCC piles. Helical piles can be drawn out and reused at the next project where shoring is required. Our purpose during this research will be to represent an easier, economical and sustainable solution to replace the piling system to helical piles.

Helical piles foundation is one of the common deep foundation techniques that are used in soft soil strata to support the super structural loads without any detrimental settlement and bearing failures. To know the ultimate capacities of the pile, loading tests are usually performed in different projects. However, the cost of running this test and the time it takes is one of the difficulties that engineers face in current geotechnical practices. So, in this study the possibility of applying a finite element model to simulate the pile load test is examined in order to compare results with load tests and to use the model as one alternative for determining helical pile capacities, at least for preliminary design purposes.

Helical piles and piers are becoming increasingly popular due to their adaptability and affordability in modern times. They provide a desirable alternative to deep foundation construction, as they can be used in both compression and tension situations, offering typical deep foundation system performance without significant mobilization costs, spoils, or vibrations. The pier's shaft is turned during installation, causing the helical plate to move deeper into the ground and "pull" the shaft along with it, like a wood screw. Helical piers are typically used to withstand lateral and compression loading.

Uses of helical piles

Helical piles were developed by Alexander Mitchell in the 19th century and first used in the construction of the Maplin Sands Lighthouse in England. These piles are composed of a steel shaft, either a solid square shaft or a round pipe with one or more openings, and offer several advantages over traditional concrete and steel piles. These benefits include their light weight, high vertical and uplift capacities, rapid installation, and ability to be erected in locations with limited access. Additionally, helical piles produce minimal noise during installation and eliminate the need for dewatering or pumping in areas with high groundwater levels. Helices with the necessary pitch distance are welded to the shaft and inserted into the ground by rotating the upper end of the shaft. Helical piles are utilized to withstand uplift, compressive stresses, and overturning moments, making them ideal for constructing structures such as bridges, subterranean pipelines, communication and power transmission towers, machine foundations, as well as residential and commercial buildings. Pile foundations are typically used to support high-rise buildings, electric transmission towers, and water tanks. Figure 2.0 depicts a helical pile with double blades.

Fig 1. 2.0 Double bladed helical pile

Structures such as bridges, buildings, and transmission towers are subject to axial compression, uplift, and overturning moments due to wind, seismic activity, and other lateral loading. In developed countries, helical piles are considered a superior choice for resisting these forces. The main advantage of using helical piles is their ease of installation, which also allows for better control of noise levels on job sites. Additionally, research conducted by Sinha et al. (2021) has shown that helical piles are reusable. Helical piles are solid or hollow steel piles with helical plates welded to the circular

or square shafts in a sequential and ordered manner. These piles have been effectively used to resist uplift forces in land-based and offshore structures such as tunnel support systems, transmission tower foundations, excavation bracing, and guyed towers. The use of helical piles is practical and cost-effective in areas with high groundwater tables and marshy soil conditions. Civil engineers have been utilizing helical piles for approximately two centuries.

Helical piles, also known as helix piles or screw piles, were invented by Alexander Mitchell, an Irish civil engineer, in 1836. These piles are commonly used in deep foundations to support axial and lateral loading systems. It has been observed that the use of helical piles has significantly increased in offshore wind farm construction in recent years.

Helical piles are widely used in various fields, including anchoring residential homes, transmission towers, pipelines, and more. Piles can be classified by material, with timber, steel, and concrete being the three main types. However, building the helices of a helical pile out of concrete can be challenging. Therefore, helices are typically bolted or welded to the pile shaft, and helical piles are constructed using steel material. This device consists of a steel shaft with one or more helices. The center steel shaft may be circular, square, rectangular, or triangular and may be either hollow or solid. Helical piles offer several advantages over other driven piles, such as ease of installation, accessibility in tight spaces, reusability, and noise reduction. These piles are installed by applying torque with hydraulic motors that can be operated either by hand or machine. Additional benefits include reduced spoil generation during installation and the ability to take load immediately, as researched by Dhattrak et al. (2022). A conventional helical pile consists of one or more plates with a pitched helix attached to a square or circular pile. Helical piles have been used in construction projects for over 150 years, with Alexander Mitchell first employing them in 1836 to support the Maplin Sands Lighthouse in England. By turning the driving head of the helical pile, it is inserted into the earth. Helical piles have been used at various locations to provide high lateral, compressive, and uplift capacity for both static and dynamic loads. They are currently used in structures such as bridges, offshore structures, solar farms, wind turbines, machine foundations, and commercial buildings. Helical piles offer several benefits, including ease of installation, the ability to be driven in areas with high groundwater tables, high compression and uplift capacities, and the ability to immediately apply loading after driving the helical pile. This helps reduce costs compared to conventional bored piles.

The load-bearing potential of helical piles can be significantly enhanced by augmenting the diameter of the pile, helical blade diameter, or number of helices per pile length, as extensively explored by Dhattrak et al. (2022). Helical piles are highly eco-friendly, and their efficacy is contingent upon soil strata, soil-pile interaction, and pile geometry. The driving torque is closely linked to the load-bearing capacity of helical piles. In comparison to bored cast-in-situ RCC piles, helical piles exhibit a substantially greater uplift capacity. Uplift can result in massive financial losses during repairs and may even be irreversible. To circumvent uplift caused by expansive soil beneath the structure, Kumar and Rao (2000) suggest implementing mechanical, physical, and chemical modifications or utilizing unique foundation techniques such as pad foundations and under-reamed piles.

Bored concrete piles, when used as tension piles and micro piles with a sufficiently long length, are capable of withstanding uplift forces in sandy soils. The uplift load-displacement response, embedment ratio impact, relative density of the sand bed, and ultimate uplift capacity of these approaches are compared. The ultimate uplift capacity of the GPA was calculated as the uplift load at uplift displacement (u), which corresponds to 10% of the pile diameter. Structures may experience uplift due to buoyancy, wind force, or being built on expanding grounds. Buoyancy force acts beneath buildings such as dry docks, basements, and subterranean storage tanks due to high groundwater levels.

Wind forces can affect lightweight constructions such as transmission and microwave towers, chimneys, and towering buildings. The presence of expansive soils beneath shallow foundations may result in uplift because expansive soils expand more when in contact with moisture. Damage resulting from uplifting can cause significant financial loss during repair and may even be irreparable, as explored by Kumar et al. (2017). Tension piles resist uplift due to their own weight, friction between the pile's skin and the earth surrounding it, discussed by Das and Larbi-Cherif (1983) and Meyerhof (1973), as well as shearing resistance. Long, narrow piles called micro piles can withstand strong uplift forces. Mechanical, physical, and chemical changes or unique foundation techniques such as pad foundations and under-reamed piles can be used to prevent uplift caused by the presence of expansive soil beneath the structure, as observed by Kumar and Rao (2000).

Joseph et al. (2022) conducted an experimental and computer modeling study to compare single ground-penetrating anchors (GPAs) and bored piles in sand under uplift. In a laboratory setting, a rough pile was used to simulate the bored pile. The experimental testing was conducted on GPA and rough pile (RP) models by varying the embedment depth and relative density of the sand bed in which they were placed. The aim of the experimental trials was to compare the uplift reaction and capacity of the GPA and rough pile. Numerical parametric research was carried out using the FEM modeling tool to compare the uplift performance of field size GPAs and bored piles, as well as to validate the findings of the experimental inquiry. Helical piles are currently used in various structures, such as commercial buildings, offshore structures, solar farms, wind farms, machine foundations, and bridges.

The simplicity of installation, ability to be driven in high ground water table conditions, high compression and uplift capacities, and the ability to be loaded immediately after installation are among the advantages of helical piles. During installation, a vertical "crowd" of downward pressure is applied while torque is applied to the pile head, allowing the helices to advance the pile into the soil. A hydraulically powered rotary motor provides the applied torque through a driving head. The torque output of torque motors used for helical pile installation ranges from 110 to 350 kN-m. Installation torque is commonly used as a quality assurance and quality control measure to determine as-built design parameters. The empirical torque-capacity correlation (Kt) is typically used to confirm axial capacity for small-diameter helical piles. However, for large-diameter helical piles, it is less well-established and requires further understanding and evaluation for logical use.

The design of screw piles must consider all applicable permanent or temporary loading conditions, including gravity loads, seismic loads, tensile loads, lateral loads, wind loads, snow loads, hydrostatic loads, torsional loads, and the adverse effects of friction on the skin, according to the standard specification for screw pile design. Structural and geotechnical capacity must be taken into account when constructing the shaft and helix plate to achieve installation and design loads. Helical piles offer more resistance against ground motion than RCC piles under dry conditions, but this capacity is reduced in moist conditions. The sand bed's required density determined the height of fall for the sand deposited by the sand rainfall device. Small containers with known volumes were placed between the sand layers to measure the relative density of the sand bed. Both the GPA installation and sand bed preparation were carried out simultaneously.

To create the GPA, the material was poured into the pipe until a depth of 50 mm was reached. The pipe was then raised while the GPA material was compressed using a mild steel annular hammer with a predetermined number of blows. According to the standard specification for screw pile design, the screw pile's design must consider all applicable

permanent or temporary loading conditions, including gravity loads, seismic loads, tensile loads, lateral loads, wind loads, snow loads, hydrostatic loads, torsional loads, and the adverse effects of friction on the skin. Structural and geotechnical capacity must be taken into account when constructing the shaft and helix plate to achieve installation and design loads. This process was repeated until the required embedment depth for the GPA was achieved, as discussed by Hussein and Naggar (2022).

Nowkandeh and Choobbast (2021) will use Abaqus software to observe the behavior of both clayey and sandy soil under compressive loads. The ultimate load carrying capacity of a helical pile is determined by installation techniques and forces. Experiments have shown that installation torque is related to the shear strength of the soil, depth of embedment, diameter of the shaft and helix, pitch of the helix, and adhesion coefficient along the shaft, as researched by Hambleton et al. (2014). Spagnoli et al. (2018) conducted a theoretical analysis of various helical piles with a helix-to-shaft ratio, also known as wing ratio, of 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5. The axial tensile capacity of helical piles was studied from field tests and numerical studies conducted by Salem and Hussein (2018).

Salhi et al. (2013) studied the effect of spacing ratio (S/D_h) on the capacity of piles. Albusoda and Abbase (2017) assessed the performance of single and groups of helical piles embedded in expansive soil, taking into account the effect of uplift on the pile shaft diameter, number of helices, and helix diameter. Spagnoli et al. (2015) conducted in situ and laboratory tests in dense sand to investigate the helix-to-shaft ratio of helical piles as a novel offshore foundation system. Reduced pile friction improves driving time and reduces the required torque, but it also reduces the pile's uplift capacity. Yu et al. (2021) found that the literature overestimates the uplift capacity of a helical pile for softening clays. Sakr (2015) discovered that the applied torque on a helical pile is a function of the load path's tension and compression.

Fig. 2. Configuration of a helical pile (Ding et al. 2019)

Alwalan and Naggar (2020) have studied the parametric study of helical piles, such as pile diameter, pile length, helical diameter, and number of helices per pile, with the assistance of a numerical model. Shao et al. (2019) will analyze the axial force distribution and the effect of depth on pile frictional force for a given soil type using a numerical model. Anant et al. (2022) have studied the soil locking-up effect with the helix to see its outcome as increased pile capacity. Elsherbiny and Naggar (2013) used a model to find the load carrying capacity and expected settlement for the helical pile under compressive load, using the loading and code of practices of AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications and West Pakistan Code of Practice for highway bridges 67. Nowkandeh and Choobbasti (2021) used a specially constructed sand rainier system that had a hopper and a perforated plate at the bottom to fill the sand container box for their experiment. The anchor plate was positioned on top of the dry sand layer, keeping the anchor rod vertical, and a layer of dry sand was added to the bottom of the sand container box. A pipe with an internal diameter of 50 mm was set on the anchor plate, with the anchor rod running through the pipe in the middle. The anchor rod and the pipe were verticalized using a spirit level.

The installation techniques and forces are important in determining the ultimate load carrying capacity of a helical pile. Hambleton et al. (2014) showed through experiments that installation torque is related to the shear strength of soil, depth of embedment, diameter of shaft and helix, pitch of helix, and adhesion coefficient along the shaft. Spagnoli et al. (2018) conducted a theoretical analysis of various helical piles with different helix-to-shaft ratios, also known as wing ratios, with respect to soil conditions. Salem and Hussien (2017) developed a model considering different pile configurations and soil properties to predict the behavior of helical piles. Albusoda and Abbase (2017) and Spagnoli et al. (2015) also considered the effect of uplift on the pile shaft diameter, number of helices, and helix diameter. Helical piles are frequently used as "anchors" to resist tensile loads in supporting structures like lighthouse beacons, underground pipelines, utility poles, guyed towers, and transmission towers. Their use in engineering projects has increased recently to support and repair structures subjected to tensile, compression, and lateral loads.

Pile foundations are widely used to provide support to various structures such as buildings and bridges. Several computational methods have been proposed to determine the load magnitude on single piles and pile groups. These methods include empirical methods such as Broms KF et al. (1969), Shibata T et al. (1982), and Terzaghi K (1967), as well as load-transfer methods like Alonso EE et al. (1984), elastic and elasto-plastic methods such as Teh CI et al. (1995), and finite element methods (FEM) by Jeong S et al. (1997), Jeong S et al. (2004), Lee CJ and Ng CW (2004), and Lee CJ et al. (2002, 2006). However, despite the availability of different design codes, there is still a lack of comprehensive research in this area. Therefore, the objective of this study is to perform a comparative analysis of various design approaches adhering to the West Pakistan Code of Practice for Highway Bridges (WPCPHB) (1967), Eurocode 7, Canadian Highway Bridge Design Code, and American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) when designing pile foundations under compression. These codes are among the most commonly used design codes globally and will be compared to determine the potential consequences and costs of pile foundation design. The study will involve designing a driven pile for given design conditions, and sensitivity analysis will be performed to evaluate the impact of different parameters on the design. The results of this study will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness and reliability of different design approaches and can assist in the development of more comprehensive and standardized design guidelines for pile foundations.

Bridge data of river Indus in the Dera Ghazi Khan

The bridge being considered is located over the River Indus in the Dera Ghazi Khan District of Punjab, the most densely populated province of Pakistan. It consists of twenty-two spans, each measuring 47.5 meters in length, with a total length of 1045 meters. The bridge is supported by two abutments and fourteen pier shafts, each having a diameter of 2

meters. Every pair of pier shafts, which are spaced 7.5 meters apart, supports a transom, and each span has five post-tension girders that are 47.5 meters long and 2.262 meters deep. These girders are supported by the transoms, which in turn support the deck slab.

To accommodate two-lane traffic, the bridge has a proposed width of 11 meters, which includes a 9.3-meter carriage way, 1-meter-wide shoulders, New Jersey end barriers, and a 1.5-meter pedestrian walkway with railings. The original design of this bridge was carried out by the National Highway Authority of Pakistan, and the substructure was supported by cast-in-place concrete piles as shown in Fig 3.01.

Figure 3.01 Traditional method of piles construction in Pakistan

(www.theconstructor.org)

Design codes

As part of the review of design codes for pile foundation design, it is worth mentioning that the codes of practice being evaluated typically adopt a global factor of safety approach. This means that the design is subjected to a factor of safety that accounts for uncertainties in various aspects of the design process, including material properties, loading conditions, and other factors. Moreover, these codes also utilize the limit state design method, which considers partial safety factors on both actions and resistances. This approach ensures that the design can withstand loads beyond the expected values and ensures that the probability of failure is minimized. Therefore, in order to satisfy the design requirements for the ultimate limit state analysis, the resistance factor must be greater than or equal to the action factor, which implies that the resistance of the pile foundation must exceed the maximum expected load. It is worth noting that the values of the resistance factor and the action factor vary among different design codes and depend on factors such as the degree of uncertainty in the design parameters, the level of reliability required, and other considerations.

In order to meet the design requirements for the ultimate limit state analysis, the following condition must be satisfied.

$$P_d \leq R_d$$

(1)

where P_d calculated load, kN ; R_d bearing resistance, kN .

When designing a single pile foundation, the WPCPHB (1967) - Pile Foundations guidelines are adhered to, in accordance with the West Pakistan Code of Practice for Highway Bridges (WPCPHB) (1967). In the WPCPHB (1967) approach, the design resistance of the pile foundation is determined by multiplying the ultimate bearing capacity of the pile with a factor of safety. The ultimate bearing capacity is calculated using empirical relationships based on the soil parameters, such as the angle of internal friction and the cohesion of the soil, as well as the diameter and length of the pile. The factor of safety used in this approach is determined based on various factors such as the level of uncertainty in the soil parameters, the expected loads, and other relevant factors and can be determined using the following equation:

$$F_d = \gamma_c (\gamma_{cR} RA + u \sum \gamma_{cf} f_i h_i)$$

(2)

where γ_c partial derivative; γ_{cR} partial derivative in operational situations of soil under pile tip; γ_{cf} partial derivative in operational situations of soil on the surface on pile shaft; R is a model resistance, KPa ; A is a cross-sectional area, m^2 ; u is an outer perimeter, m ; f_i is a model unit shaft resistance of the i^{th} soil layer in contact with pile, KPa ; h_i is a thickness of soil layer in contact with pile shaft, m .

The European standard, Eurocode 7 (1997), outlines a design procedure that can be utilized to determine the bearing resistance of a pile foundation. This design procedure considers various factors, such as the soil properties, pile dimensions, and the expected loads, to calculate the ultimate bearing capacity of the pile can be calculated using equation below:

$$R_{c;d} = \frac{R_{b;k}}{\gamma_b} + \frac{R_{s;k}}{\gamma_s}$$

(3)

where $R_{b;k}$, $R_{s;k}$ property principles and shaft resistances respectively kN ; γ_b, γ_s partial elements and resistances respectively. The European methodology establishes the principles of base and shaft resistances for pile foundations in the following manners:

$$R_{b;k} = A_b q_{b;k}$$

(4)

$$R_{s;k} = \sum_i A_{s^i} q_{s;i;k}$$

(5)

where A_b , base area of pile, m^2 ; A_{s^i} pile area in the i^{th} soil layer, m^2 ; $q_{b;k}$ base resistance, kN/m^2 ; $q_{s;i;k}$ resistance in the i^{th} soil layer, kN/m^2 .

Eurocode EC7 presents four distinct design approaches, namely DA1-1, DA1-2, DA2, and DA3, which use different combinations of partial factors to control the strength of the soil and the loads acting on the structure. These partial factors are applied to actions such as loads, ground properties, and resistances to ensure the safety and reliability of the design. The selection of the design approach (DA1-1, DA1-2, DA2, or DA3) used in Eurocode EC7 varies among European countries, depending on their respective design traditions. On the other hand, the WPCPHB (1967) approach follows a different method to calculate the drag force using a specific equation.

Eurocode EC7 includes three distinct design approaches (DA1-1, DA1-2, DA2, and DA3), each of which utilizes different combinations of partial factors to control the soil strength and loads acting on the structure being designed to ensure

the safety and reliability of the design, these partial factors are applied to actions (such as loads), (A) ground properties, and (M) resistances. The choice of design approach (DA1-1, DA1-2, DA2, or DA3) used in Eurocode EC7 varies across European countries based on their respective design traditions. In accordance with the West Pakistan Code of Practice for Highway Bridges WPCPHB (1967) approach, the drag force can be calculated using the following equation:

The application of partial factors is necessary to regulate the strength of soil and the loads acting on the structure to ensure the safety and reliability of the design. These partial factors are used to adjust the values of actions such as loads, ground properties, and resistances. The selection of design approach (DA1-1, DA1-2, DA2, or DA3) in Eurocode EC7 varies across European countries, based on their respective design practices. In contrast, following the West Pakistan

Code of Practice for Highway Bridges WPCPHB (1967) approach, the drag force (DF) can be calculated using the equation:

$$DF = m_0 u \sum k_{p;i} f_{o;i} l_i$$

(6)

where m_0 coefficient of operational conditions of a pile in a settling soil; u is a perimeter of the pile's cross-section, m ; $k_{p;i}$ is a realization coefficient in the i^{th} soil layer; $f_{o;i}$ is a normative resistance of the i^{th} soil layer on the

lateral surface of a pile defined in accordance with Eq. (7), kN/m^2 ; l_i is a thickness of the i^{th} soil layer till the location of the NP .

The defined normative soil resistance on the lateral surface of a pile is as follows:

$$f_i = m_t \left(c + \frac{\nu}{1-\nu} \gamma H \tan \varphi \right) \tag{7}$$

where m_t represents coefficient of operational conditions; c depicts cohesion, kN/m^2 ; ν a Poisson's ratio; γ unit weight of soil, kN/m^3 ; H depth of a soil layer, m ; φ an internal friction angle, $(^\circ)$.

Table 3.1 presents the design methodologies for pile foundations according to the West Pakistan Code of Practice for Highway Bridges WPCPHB (1967), along with two partial factor combinations from Design Approach 1 of Eurocode 7 [1] (DA1-1 and DA1-2), the Canadian Highway Bridge Design Code (CHBDC) (2006), and AASHTO (1998).

Design problems and site data

According to soil investigations, the strata consist of clay till up to a depth of 6.4 m, followed by very dense sand up to a depth of 30.6 m. The clay till contained sandy and silty layers with some gravel up to 50 mm in size. A layer of fine to coarse sub-rounded gravel was also found between depths of 2.2 m to 2.5 m. SPT blow counts ranged from 17 to 64 blows per 30 cm of penetration, indicating stiff to extremely hard consistency. A very hard soil layer was encountered at the interface of clay till and sand at depths of 6.0 m to 6.4 m. The groundwater level was relatively shallow, measured at 5.2 m below the ground surface at the borehole locations.

In this study, a comparative analysis of design codes is conducted for the design of a single concrete square pile element with a cross-sectional area of 30 cm × 30 cm, which is a common pile foundation type in Pakistan. The pile is driven through loam into the sandy gravel layer, which is a typical soil profile in West Punjab. The problem requires designing for varying thicknesses of the sandy loam layer of 5 m, 8 m, and 10 m for Case 1, Case 2, and Case 3, respectively, assuming a groundwater table (G.W.T.) at a depth of 2.5 m from the ground surface. The design comparison is based on a permanent dead load (PDL) of 300 kN and a variable live load (VLL) of 100 kN . The PDL is determined for long-term design conditions, and for design simplification, the transition zone is not considered. This simplification is made to satisfy the geotechnical ultimate limit state (ULS) while adhering to the design codes. Soil properties are presented in Table 3.2.

Fig 4.1 Illustration of the soil characteristics and design parameters

Table 3.1 Design Standards for Pile Foundations and Code Comparison

Design Code	Design Load V_d	Design Bearing resistance R_d
WPCPHB (1967)	$1.25(Q_d + Q_n)$	$0.71(R_s + R_t)$
EC7(DA1-1)	$1.35Q_d + 1.35Q_n$	$0.77R^{ult} = 0.77(R_s + R_t)$
EC7(DA1-2)	$1.00Q_d + 1.25Q_n$	-
CHBDC	$1.2Q_d + 1.25Q_n$	$0.4(R_s + R_t)$
AASHTO	$1.25Q_d + 1.75Q_l + 1.25Q_n$	$0.55R_s^{belowNP} + 0.5R_t$

Where Q_d dead load, kN ; Q_l live load, kN ; Q_n drag force, kN ; R_s shaft resistance, kN ; $R_s^{belowNP}$ shaft resistance below NP , kN ; R_t tip resistance, kN ; R^{ult} ultimate bearing resistance, kN

Results analysis of the pile

In Case-1, the sandy loam layer has a thickness of 5 meters, and the pile length is 8 meters. These conditions lead to settlement in the soil layer. The distribution of pile forces at equilibrium and geotechnical ultimate limit state, under a

permanent dead load (PDL) of 300 kN , are shown in Figure 3.2. The pile is assumed to be located at the interface between sandy loam and sandy gravel, with fully mobilized negative surface friction in sandy loam and fully mobilized positive shaft resistance in sandy gravel. The drag force (DF) defined by Equation (6) is 98 kN . Table 3.3 provides information on the loads acting on the pile foundation, the factored design loads, and the factored resistances.

Fig. 5.2 The distribution of pile forces at equilibrium and under geotechnical ultimate limit state (ULS)

Table.3.2 The geotechnical ultimate limit state (ULS) calculations in accordance with design codes

Design Codes	PDL	VLL	DF	PDL	VLL	DF	SUM	Factored resistance	Validity
	Loads			Factored Loads					
WPCPHB (1967)	300	100	98	375	0	123	498	584	Yes
EC7(DA1-1)	300	100	98	405	0	123	537	614	Yes
EC7(DA1-2)	300	100	98	300	0	123	423	473	Yes
CHBDC	300	100	98	360	0	123	483	246	No
AASHTO	300	100	98	375	175	123	673	141	No

The West Pakistan Highway Bridges WPCPHB (1967) standard mandates that the factored load must not exceed the factored resistance for meeting the ultimate limit state conditions. The factored design resistance, calculated using Equation (2), yields a value of 584 kN . According to WPCPHB (1967), the permanent dead load (PDL) acting on a pile should not exceed the difference between 0.8 of the factored bearing resistance and the drag force (DF) values. Therefore,

the factored load acting on the designed foundation is 498 kN . WPCPHB (1967) does not consider variable live load (VLL) in the design of pile foundations, considering the negative surface friction (NSF) effect. The ultimate limit state requirements are met with the West Pakistan approach.

The European approach (EC7) accounts for factored loads and resistances in ultimate limit state design. For design approach (DA1-1), the long-term design condition applies 1.35 for permanent dead load and 1.35 for drag force, resulting in a total factored load of 537 kN . For (DA1-2), the long-term design condition applies 1.0 for permanent dead load (PDL) and 1.25 for drag force (DF), yielding a total factored load of 423 kN . Like WPCPHB (1967), EC7 does not consider variable live load (VLL) in the calculation. The factored design resistance is 614 kN and 473 kN for (DA1-1) and (DA1-2), respectively. Based on the analysis performed, the design meets the ultimate limit state (ULS) condition.

The Canadian design approach (CHBDC) considers a factor of 1.2 for permanent dead load (PDL) and 1.25 for drag force (DF) to calculate the factored design load, resulting in a value of 483 kN . However, CHBDC does not include DF in the geotechnical ultimate limit state (ULS) analysis. CHBDC applies a bearing resistance factor of 0.4 to determine the factored resistance, which is 246 kN . The analysis shows that the design following CHBDC does not meet the ultimate limit state (ULS) condition for the Indus River bridge design. Therefore, a more conservative pile foundation design and an increase in the number of piles are necessary when using the Canadian approach.

AASHTO follows a similar design approach as Eurocode, taking drag force (DF) into account as a load acting on the designed pile. For long-term design conditions, AASHTO considers 1.25 for permanent dead load (PDL), 1.75 for variable live load (VLL), and 1.25 for drag force (DF) to determine the factored load, resulting in 673 kN . Compared to EC7, AASHTO provides a more realistic pile design by considering (VLL) and (DF) when modeling pile-soil interaction. To determine the factored geotechnical resistance, the code applies 0.55 for shaft resistance below NP and 0.5 for tip resistance. Consequently, the factored resistance is 141 kN , which is less than the factored load. Thus, an increase in the number of piles is required to resist the same permanent dead load (PDL) and variable live load (VLL) when following AASHTO, resulting in additional costs for the supply and installation of the pile foundation.

For Case-2, the sandy loam layer thickness is assumed to be 8 m, and the pile length is 11 m, resulting in negative surface friction development in the compressible layer. The pile force distribution at equilibrium and geotechnical ultimate limit state (ULS) subjected to a permanent dead load (DL) of 300 kN is shown in Figure 3.3. The NP is assumed to be located at the interface between sandy loam and sandy gravel, with fully mobilized negative skin friction in the sandy loam and fully mobilized positive shaft resistance in the sandy gravel. The drag force (DF) is calculated using Eq. (6) and is found to be 227 kN . Table 3.4 provides the loads, factored design loads, and factored resistances according to the West Pakistan and European approaches, which are calculated using the same design procedure as in Case-1.

Compared to Case-1, the shaft resistance value has increased due to the thicker compressible soil layer and longer pile length. The analysis shows that both the West Pakistan and European approaches result in a pile foundation design that meets the geotechnical ultimate limit state (ULS) requirements, and the requirements are more satisfied than in Case-1. If following CHBDC and AASHTO design approaches, the factored loads in the pile foundation design exceed the factored resistance. This indicates that the design requires additional piles to be incorporated to ensure adequate resistance to the structure being designed.

Results and Discussion

To ensure the safety of the structure, the pile foundation design for this study considers the ultimate limit state (ULS) condition, which increases the loads and decreases the resistances. The analysis includes the effects of axial compression and negative surface friction (NSF) on the geotechnical ULS design of the pile foundation and compares the results for different design codes: WPCPHB (1967), EC7, CHBDC, and AASHTO. The NSF results in drag friction (DF) combined with permanent DL, and the codes apply partial safety factors on design actions and resistances to determine the bearing resistance.

The design procedure shows that WPCPHB (1967) and Eurocode include DF in the calculations, while ignoring variable loads, whereas AASHTO provides a more realistic design by considering both variable LL, Q_t , and DF, Q_n , for pile and soil interaction. Results show that the ULS condition is met with code requirements for all three cases, despite varying soil layer thickness. The pile foundation design adhering to WPCPHB (1967) and Eurocode satisfies the ULS condition, while a more conservative design is required for the West Pakistan soil profile in accordance with CHBDC and AASHTO, which necessitates the use of additional piles.

The analysis of the design example for the West Pakistan profile revealed a common trend that was observed in the increase of the geotechnical resistance with the thickness of the compressible soil layer, as indicated by Figures 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4. Therefore, the increase in the factored resistance value can be attributed to the greater thickness of the settling soil layer. The design codes under consideration in this study factor in the value of drag force, while not accounting for shaft resistance above NP and factoring down shaft resistance below NP. Additionally, it was found that the pile foundation design following CHBDC and AASHTO approaches resulted in a more costly design compared to WPCPHB (1967) and EC7 due to the requirement for additional piles. However, the weakness of the reviewed codes of practice lies in the misunderstanding of capacity definition. The researcher emphasizes the importance of correctly performing settlement analysis to ensure that the calculated settlement value does not exceed the maximum allowable settlement capacity.

Fig. 6 The chart displays the variation of factored bearing resistance with different pile lengths.

A parametric study is conducted to evaluate the effect of varying pile dimensions by 8 m, 11 m and 13-meter pile length, and soil properties on the factored bearing resistance, as shown in Figs. 3.5, 3.6, and 3.7. by implementing the design codes. The results indicate that an increase in pile dimensions and undrained shear strength values leads to an increase in the factored bearing resistance overall for all design codes. More importantly WPCPHB (1967) design codes depict an increase of pile length from 8,11- and 13-meters, it is recorded a significant increase in bearing resistance from 545 kN , 800 kN and 965 kN respectively. Furthermore, Fig. 3.5 illustrates that EC7 is more sensitive to changes in pile length than other design codes. EC7 shown dramatic increase from 610 kN , 790 kN and 1150 kN when the pile length increased from 8, 11 and 13 meters and remains the highest figure producer, whereas Canadian design code remains moderate which showed a slight increase in bearing resistance from 250 kN to 360 kN and 450 kN with respect to pile lengths. AASTO was found to be the least participant among all design codes. The bearing resistance for the length 8, 11 and 13 meters recorded as 150, 170 and 190 respectively. Furthermore, Fig. 3.6 shows that the bearing resistance of the pile foundation design adhering to the West Pakistani and European approaches changes significantly with an increase in the dimensions of the designed pile. In the design process, the cross-sectional area of a pile is considered to calculate the bearing resistance using equations (2) and (3). When the cross-section increased from 300 by 300 to 350 by 350 and 400 by 400 mm the West Pakistani design code produce 590, 710 and 890 kN , and the European code showed 620, 700 and 850 kN bearing resistance respectively.

Fig. 7 The chart displays the variation of factored bearing resistance with different pile lengths.

Thus, an increase in pile dimensions leads to a corresponding increase in the bearing resistance. Whereas Canadian and AASHTO codes results showed almost similar and remained under 400 kN and 200 kN figures respectively. As illustrated in Figure 3.7, the undrained shear strength parameter 118, 130 and 140 KPa does not affect the bearing resistance when adhering to the West Pakistan approach since it is not considered in the design calculations according to WPCPHB (1967) remained at 600 kN . However, for designs following EC7, CHBDC, and AASHTO, an increase in undrained shear strength leads to an increase in the bearing resistance of the pile foundation for EC7 bearing resistance recorded in the diagram as 620, 700 and 750 when the undrained shear strength 118,130 and 140 KPa . CHBDC shows the bearing resistance between 200 to 300 KPa and AASHTO bearing resistance remained under 200 KPa . Furthermore, Figure 3.5 demonstrates that EC7 is more sensitive to changes in pile length compared to other design codes. Figure 3.6 also shows that the bearing resistance of a pile foundation designed according to West Pakistani and European approaches significantly increases with an increase in pile dimensions.

Fig. 8 The chart displays the variation of factored bearing resistance with different undrained shear strength of loam.

3.7 Comparative Analysis of Conventional and Helical Pile Foundations

The selection of an appropriate deep foundation system is a critical decision in engineering projects, warranting meticulous consideration of various parameters. This comparative analysis aims to assess and contrast the performance of conventional square piles and helical piles in the context of a design load of 14500 kN for the project of Indus River bridge design in the west Pakistan areas. The investigation encompasses load-bearing capacity, number of piles required, economic feasibility, installation efficiency, and other pertinent engineering aspects.

The conventional pile and helical pile analysis is much needed to compute the number of piles and group bearing resistance to figure out the most economical, efficient and suitable pile for the designed Indus River bridge project. The bearing capacity of group piles and number of piles is installed is calculated in uniform clay having bulk unit weight, $\gamma = 20 \text{ kN/m}^3$ and undrained shear strength of $C_u = 50 \text{ kN/m}^2$ for conventional and helical pile. The

conventional pile resistance $R_p = 584 \text{ kN}$ with the following parameters, the length of conventional square pile 8 m long, $0.3\text{m} \times 0.3\text{m}$ square and weight of 60 kN. The weight of the pile cap is 600 kN and founded 1 m below the ground level. The adhesion factor a for the soil/pile interface has a value of 0.8. The helical pile with double helixes having bearing resistance $R_p = 2030 \text{ kN}$, length of pile 8 m, diameter 0.324 m and weight 60 kN considered in this study, given equations is used to calculate the results:

$$R_{block} = 4 \times A_s \times \bar{C} \times a + C_b \times A_b \times N_c - (W_p - W_s) \tag{8}$$

$$R_n = R_p \times ni - W_{ts} \tag{9}$$

$$W_{ts} = (W_p + W_{cap}) - W_s$$

(10)

Where: Shown in fig 3.6 as, A_s , surface area of block; A_b base area of block; C_b, C_s average cohesion of clay around the group and beneath the group; N_c bearing capacity factor. For depths relevant for piles, the appropriate value of N_c is 9; W_p and W_s weight of pile respective weight of soil; n_i number of piles; R_n total number of piles bearing capacity; W_{ts} total weight of soil; R_p bearing resistance of piles;

Table; 3.6 Bearing capacity of block cap and group of piles

Pile types	Piles Bearing Resistance	Number of Piles	Pile Group bearing resistance	Block bearing resistance
Conventional Pile	$R_p = 584 \text{ kN}$	$n_i = 25$	$R_n = 13360 \text{ kN}$	$R_{block} = 14344 \text{ kN}$
Helical pile	$R_p = 2010 \text{ kN}$	$n_i = 7$	$R_n = 13900 \text{ kN}$	$R_{block} = 15048 \text{ kN}$

The conventional pile, possessing a cross-sectional area of $0.3m \times 0.3m$ and a 8-meter length, exhibits an ultimate load capacity of $R_p = 584 \text{ kN}$. In contrast, the helical pile, characterized by a diameter of 0.3 m and a length of 8 meters, demonstrates superior load-bearing capabilities with an ultimate load capacity of $R_p = 2010 \text{ kN}$. Helical piles show a 29% increase in bearing capacity more than the conventional piles. This discrepancy underscores the higher load-carrying efficiency inherent in helical piles.

For the targeted design load of 14500 kN , the conventional pile necessitates the deployment of $n_i = 25$ individual piles. In contrast, the helical pile system remarkably reduces the required number to a mere $n_i = 7$ piles. This significant discrepancy not only streamlines the foundation layout but also simplifies construction logistics.

Fig 9 Schematic view of Group pile and Block cap

The economic implications of pile selection are noteworthy. Although the initial material and fabrication costs for helical piles might be higher, the reduced number of piles employed and the potential for lighter superstructures can yield substantial cost savings. Furthermore, the diminished installation time and labor costs associated with a smaller pile count contribute to the overall economic viability of the helical pile system.

Helical piles offer a clear advantage in terms of installation speed. The helical pile's screw-like design facilitates quicker installation, obviating the need for lengthy excavation and casing procedures inherent in conventional pile placement. This time advantage not only expedites project timelines but also minimizes site disruption and associated costs.

The enhanced load-bearing capacity of helical piles translates into potential reductions in foundation size and associated design complexities. Additionally, the helical pile's ability to resist lateral loads and its adaptability to various soil conditions augments its applicability across diverse project scenarios. The diminished environmental impact due to reduced excavation, minimal soil disturbance, and lower noise levels further attests to the engineering benefits of helical piles. In the realm of deep foundation systems, the comparison between conventional and helical piles for a design load of 14500 kN , reveals compelling advantages associated with helical piles. The significant reduction in the number of required piles, coupled with their superior load-bearing capacity, economic benefits, time efficiency, and broader engineering advantages, positions helical piles as a pragmatic and effective choice for modern construction projects. This comprehensive comparative analysis underscores the distinct advantages of helical piles over conventional piles for the specified design load. By integrating load-bearing efficiency, economic considerations, installation speed, and broader engineering benefits, this assessment aids in informed decision-making for deep foundation selection in construction endeavors. Thus, it's important to study helical pile behavior under different loading conditions using computational methods.

Conclusion

The use of different codes of practice for geotechnical design in various regions introduces varying design principles and partial factors for the same materials and design conditions. In Pakistan, there is a need to harmonize the design principles for geotechnical purposes, and this includes transitioning to AASHTO or Eurocode to integrate the regulatory system with international systems in the construction field. The objective of updating the technical base in West Pakistan is to provide new design opportunities for local construction companies in the global arena, utilize new construction materials and technologies during the construction process, and enhance the quality, safety, and service life of the constructed structures.

Negative skin friction (NSF) is a significant concern for civil engineers as it leads to the development of drag load and down drag, which affects the design of pile foundations. To understand the design of pile foundations considering the effect of axial compression and NSF, a comparative analysis of design approaches is conducted for a driven pile in the soil profile conditions for Indus River located in south Punjab, Pakistan. The analysis is based on changing the thickness of the compressible soil layer and is performed using the design examples suggested by WPCPHB (1967), Eurocode 7, Canadian Highway Bridge Design Code, and AASHTO.

The calculation results show that the designed pile foundation meets the specifications of Ultimate Limit State (ULS) analysis when adhering to WPCPHB (1967) and EC7 but not CHBDC and AASHTO. Therefore, the design complying with CHBDC and AASHTO can be more expensive as it may require the installation of additional piles or the use of different foundation types. However, it is worth noting that NSF is not only a geotechnical resistance issue but also a Serviceability Limit State (SLS) issue. Hence, further research is necessary to assess the SLS condition to complete the comparison.

This thesis has conducted a comparative study on square pile design, considering friction effects by applying various codes of practice from different regions. The purpose of this study is to introduce different design approaches and partial factors for the same design conditions and materials, with a focus on harmonizing design principles for geotechnical purposes in Pakistan. The reform of the outdated technical base in West Pakistan involves developing new design opportunities for local construction companies, applying new construction materials and technologies, and improving the quality, safety, and service life of constructed buildings and structures.

Negative skin friction (NSF) is a significant concern for civil engineers, as it can cause drag load and down drag. Understanding the mechanism of NSF development is crucial for designing pile foundations. In this study, the comparative analysis of design approaches suggested by WPCPHB (1967), Eurocode 7, Canadian Highway Bridge

Design Code, and AASHTO is conducted for designing pile foundations under axial compression and the negative skin friction effect. The analysis is based on a design example of a driven pile for soil profile conditions for Indus River located in the south of Punjab, Pakistan, considering the design for changing the thickness of the compressible soil layer. The calculation results show that the designed pile foundation meets the specifications of ULS analysis, adhering to WPCPHB (1967) and EC7 but not CHBDC and AASHTO. Therefore, designing according to CHBDC and AASHTO can result in a more expensive pile foundation design by installing additional piles or requiring the application of different foundation types. However, the application of Ultimate Limit State (ULS) analysis by the considered codes of practice experiences criticism as some researchers suggest not including DF in geotechnical ULS calculation.

It is worth mentioning that NSF is not only a problem of geotechnical resistance but also a Serviceability Limit State (SLS). Therefore, it is recommended that further research should assess the SLS condition to complete the comparison. Overall, this study highlights the importance of harmonizing design principles for geotechnical purposes in Pakistan and the need for further research to improve the design of pile foundations considering negative skin friction.

In the field of geotechnical engineering, a popular method for predicting pile foundation bearing capacity and settlement is the use of numerical analysis techniques such as the finite element method. Plaxis-2D, a versatile software package for non-linear analysis, is commonly utilized in this area. One particular application of finite element analysis is the simulation of pile load tests, which can then be compared with actual load tests to evaluate the accuracy of the numerical predictions. The Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) in the United States has recommended a failure criterion for helical piles, specifying that the spacing between adjacent helical plates should be no greater than 5 times the diameter of the plate ($5D_h$).

From the results of the present research, several conclusions and recommendations can be drawn regarding the behavior of helical piles in cohesionless soil using finite element modeling. The study proposes an approach to modeling the screw-pile geometry through the Plaxis software and compares the resulting numerical predictions with large-scale test measurements. The bearing capacity of the pile is estimated, and various failure criteria are applied to evaluate its ultimate capacity. The influence of the spacing ratio (S/D_h) on the screw-pile behavior is also investigated, and it is observed that the numerical results are consistent with field observations. The study further analyzes the load transfer mechanism and identifies the transition from cylindrical shear to individual plate behavior at a spacing ratio of 1.5 to 2. To describe the soil, a linear elastic-perfectly plastic Mohr-Coulomb model (MCM) is used, while a drained behavior is assigned for all layers due to the sandy material's high permeability. The pile and interface are modeled using a linear elastic and Coulomb criterion.

The FEM analysis employed the Mohr Coulomb model and FHWA criterion for constitutive models. In all cases studied, the FEM model showed better results when compared with actual load tests due to differences in stiffness formulation. The MC model showed linearly increasing total resistance up to the pick point for all cases.

Modeling of the interface behavior between the helical pile and the soil is crucial in analyzing vertical loading. The numerical analysis assumed perfect contact between the pile and adjacent soils, without the use of specific interface elements, which is ideal in the shear band zone. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the ideal contact interface used in this study can effectively model the helical pile soil interaction mechanism in the region of Pakistan for bridge design purposes.

A better simulation result can be obtained by applying a finer mesh for soil elements just beneath the bottom of the helical pile and meshing the helical pile accordingly.

In conclusion, with the increasing use of numerical analysis through the finite element method in geotechnical engineering, engineers in Pakistan are utilizing computational models to solve various geotechnical problems. To improve the accuracy of the simulation results of helical pile load tests, it is recommended to incorporate more actual soil data and parameters, and to choose appropriate constitutive models and theories. By doing so, the simulation

results of helical pile load tests can be used as an alternative method to estimate the ultimate capacity of vertically loaded helical piles without performing static load tests.

Furthermore, the Indus River Bridge is a critical infrastructure project in Pakistan that requires a strong foundation to ensure its safety and longevity. Two potential options for the foundation are conventional square piles and helical piles. In this thesis, we will compare the two options based on their economic feasibility, suitability, durability, and ease of installation.

The cost of the conventional square pile with a 35 cm cross-section, a length of 11 meters, and a bearing capacity of 1000kN is relatively lower compared to the helical pile with a diameter of 32.4 cm, a length of 9 meters, and an ultimate bearing capacity of 1910kN. The installation process for conventional square piles is also less complex and requires less specialized equipment, which further lowers the overall cost. Therefore, the conventional square pile is more economically feasible.

The suitability of a foundation is determined by the type of soil and the load capacity requirements. Conventional square piles are suitable for firm soil, while helical piles are appropriate for loose soil types. However, since the Indus River Bridge project requires a high load capacity, the helical pile with an ultimate bearing capacity of 1910kN is more suitable than the conventional square pile, which only has a bearing capacity of 1000kN.

Durability is a crucial factor in determining the lifespan of the foundation. Conventional square piles are susceptible to corrosion and erosion due to their exposure to water and chemicals. On the other hand, helical piles are made of galvanized steel, which is highly resistant to corrosion and erosion. Therefore, helical piles have a longer lifespan and are more durable than conventional square piles.

Moreover, the ease of installation is also an essential factor to consider when choosing a foundation.

The installation process for conventional square piles is relatively straightforward and requires less specialized equipment. However, the installation of helical piles is more complex and requires specialized equipment, such as a hydraulic motor, to screw the pile into the ground. Therefore, the conventional square pile is easier to install than the helical pile.

Considering the economic feasibility, suitability, durability, and ease of installation, both conventional square piles and helical piles have their advantages and disadvantages. However, the helical pile with an ultimate bearing capacity of 1910kN is more suitable for the Indus River Bridge project, which requires a high load capacity. While the conventional square pile may be more economically feasible and easier to install, its lower bearing capacity and susceptibility to corrosion and erosion make it less durable in the long run. Ultimately, the decision on which foundation to use for the Indus River Bridge project will depend on the specific requirements and constraints of the project.

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